

A0510

Using high-entropy materials to produce green hydrogen from alkaline water electrolysis

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Abstract

Hydrogen is a clean and sustainable alternative to fossil fuels. A variety of methods are used to produce it, each of which has a different environmental impact. The main impact of the technology developed in this research is related to sustainable H₂ production, which can meet an increasing share of the hydrogen demand for various applications. Green hydrogen technologies are under continuous development with a great number of applications and business sectors involved (power to gas, industry applications, residential uses, mobility etc.). One of the least expensive and most environmentally friendly production methods is alkaline water electrolysis (AWE). High-entropy materials (HEMs), which take advantage from the synergy between their multiple metallic components, have shown great potential for a wide variety of applications, including AWE. The development and engineering of novel nanostructured HEM-based electrocatalysts, to be used in an electrolyzer employing a polymeric anion exchange membrane (AEM) as the electrolyte, is the main aim of the "HEM4GREEN" project (High-Entropy Materials as cost-effective catalysts in anion exchange membrane water electrolysis for GREEN hydrogen production). HEMs are prepared by scalable techniques, suitable for mass-production, and are evaluated as catalysts for stable operation at high current density. For this purpose, HEM-based electrodes are assembled in a zero-gap AEM-based AWE full cell, whose electrochemical performance is evaluated comparatively against proper benchmarks.

This study aims to evaluate low-entropy CoNi- and NiFe-based materials as reference electrocatalysts, providing a foundational comparison for the subsequent development and assessment of high-entropy materials. CoNi- and NiFe-oxides for the anode and CoNi- and NiFe-alloys for the cathode are synthesized and investigated in terms of physico- and electro-chemical properties.

Introduction

To achieve stable and affordable energy access by 2050, more Countries are committing to achieving net-zero emissions [1,2]. This requires significant investments in research, development, and infrastructure to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy sources [3]. Due to the intermittent nature of many renewable energy sources, hydrogen presents an excellent low-emission alternative. Despite its current limitations, hydrogen continues to gain popularity as a clean, versatile energy carrier. Efforts to scale up low-emission H₂ production are increasing, with a focus on carbon capture and storage, as well as renewable water electrolysis [4,5]. Hydrogen is considered the ideal replacement for conventional fuels.

AWE is a mature technology capable of H₂ production at the megawatt scale and remains one of the most widely used commercial electrolytic technologies worldwide. Its widespread adoption is largely due to the adaptability of these systems to various scales for distributed energy needs, as well as the use of inexpensive raw materials for liquid-electrolyte water electrolysis. The low cost of diaphragm separators, non-precious metal electrocatalysts for hydrogen and oxygen evolution reactions, and the use of steel bipolar plates are key advantages of AWE. However, a significant drawback is the use of a corrosive alkaline liquid electrolyte (e.g., 7-10 M KOH), which leads to high deterioration rates across the system and demands careful management in terms of recirculation and regeneration, as it reacts strongly with carbon dioxide in the air. Additionally, liquid alkaline electrolyzers have a limited operating range, low current densities, and generate hydrogen at near ambient pressure. These systems also pose safety risks due to the direct combination of H₂ and O₂, as well as low Coulombic efficiency caused by the incomplete prevention of H₂ diffusion through the diaphragm. To address these limitations, prototypes using proton exchange membrane (PEM) separators have been demonstrated, offering advantages over conventional AWE, such as higher current densities, higher hydrogen output pressures, better dynamic behavior (faster response and wider load ranges), and higher hydrogen purity. The solid polymer membrane also shortens the ionic path between electrodes, improving efficiency. Additionally, the low gas crossover rate ensures higher hydrogen purity, enabling safe operation across a wide load range. The next step in electrolysis technology involves combining the benefits of these systems while overcoming their limitations. AEM electrolysis, still in the laboratory phase, shows promise of lower costs and greater flexibility. Key developments are needed, particularly in optimizing low-cost electrocatalysts that are resistant to fluctuations in critical raw material (CRM) availability [6].

In this context, low entropy CoNi- and NiFe-based materials prepared through via sol-gel method, are investigated as benchmark electrocatalysts for both hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and oxygen evolution reaction (OER) in a zero-gap AEM-based AWE full cell. The strong interaction between the two metals results in promising electrochemical behaviors, as evidenced by extensive investigations involving various materials and reactions.

1. Scientific Approach

1 Synthesis of electrocatalysts

1.1 OER electrocatalysts

Nanostructured bimetallic oxides for OER electrocatalysis were prepared via the sol-gel method. Nickel (II) acetate, cobalt (II) acetate, and iron acetate were used as metal sources. Stoichiometric amounts of these salts (Table 1) were dissolved in 60 g of water and mixed with citric acid as a complexing agent. The mixture was stirred at 70°C for 2 hours to form a gel, dried at 80°C overnight, and calcined in air at a controlled temperature. After calcination, the material was rapidly cooled to enhance porosity and oxygen deficiency. A reference monometallic nickel oxide was also prepared using the same method. Additionally, a nickel

hydroxide sample was synthesized by co-precipitation from nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate, neutralized with NaOH at pH 9, and then filtered, washed, and dried at 80°C overnight.

1.2 HER electrocatalysts

A portion of the as-prepared oxides was utilized to produce HER electrocatalysts for the cell cathode. Oxide powders were reduced in 5% H₂/Ar atmosphere for 30 min to form reduced bimetallic compounds. The reduction temperatures of each material were determined by means the temperature programmed reduction (TPR) analysis, carried out on an AMI-300 instrument.

1.3 Anionic electrolyte

A commercial Fumatech® FAA3-50 membrane (50 μm) was used as a solid polymer electrolyte in AEM electrolysis. Its thickness balances low cross-over, low resistance, and mechanical stability. The membrane contains ammonium groups for hydroxyl ion exchange, facilitating the OER at the anode while preventing product recombination. Prior to use, the membrane is activated by treatment in 3 M NaCl for 72 h to convert it to the Cl⁻ form, enabling ion exchange. Fumatech® ION FAA-3-SOLUTION ionomer was used as a binder to improve electrocatalyst adhesion during ink preparation.

2. Experiments

2.1 Electrochemical Characterization

The system was electrochemically characterized to evaluate membrane electrode assembly (MEA) performance at different cell potentials. Galvanostatic polarization curves, durability tests, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analyses were performed. Polarization and chrono-potentiometric curves were recorded using a Keithley power supply, PGSTAT Autolab 302 Potentiostat/Galvanostat with a 20 A booster, and a Frequency Response Analyzer (FRA) for EIS. EIS data were collected in a frequency range of 1 MHz to 10 mHz, with a 0.01 V r.m.s. sinusoidal excitation. Series resistance (R_S) was determined from the high-frequency intercept on the Nyquist plot, and polarization resistance (R_P) was estimated from the difference between low- and high-frequency intercepts [7].

3. Results

Table 1. Codes, composition and calcination temperature (T_C) of the nanostructured oxides prepared via the sol-gel method.

Code	Metal molar concentrations			$T_C / ^\circ\text{C}$
	Ni	Co	Fe	
Ni100	1.00			400
Ni85Co15_400	0.85	0.15		400
Ni85Co15_800	0.85	0.15		800
Ni50Co50_400	0.50	0.50		400
Ni50Co50_800	0.50	0.50		800
Ni85Fe15_400	0.85		0.15	400
Ni85Fe15_800	0.85		0.15	800

3.1 OER electrocatalysts

3.1.1 Morphology

The morphology and composition of all electrocatalysts was investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analyses. Figure 1 shows some representative SEM images of the OER electrocatalysts investigated. Regardless of the synthesis method, large agglomerates of small particles are formed, as proven by higher magnification images (Figure 1e). In the case of the sample (NiH100) prepared by via the co-precipitation method, the particle aggregates look more compact.

The results of SEM/EDX analysis demonstrate that the organic components of the metal precursors are completely removed during calcination, with the formation of inorganic oxides. The identification of their phase(s) was carried out via XRD analysis.

Figure 1. Morphology of the oxides as resulting from SEM analysis. The shown micrographs refer to samples (a) NiH100, (b) Ni100, (c,e) Ni85Co15_400 and (d) Ni85Fe15_400.

3.1.2 Phase(s) of the oxides

Figure 2 displays the XRD patterns of mono- and bi-metallic oxides. XRD analysis confirms the formation of a single β -Ni(OH)₂ phase in the sample (NiH100) synthesized by co-precipitation (top of Figure 2a). The monometallic Ni100 oxide synthesized via the sol-gel exhibits only cubic NiO reflections [(111), (200), (220), (311), (222)] at $\sim 37.30^\circ$, 43.34° , 62.89° , 75.45° , and 79.40° 2θ -angles (bottom of Figure 2a), indicating a pure rock-salt (RS) structure.

For bimetallic oxides (Figure 2b–d), phase composition varies with metal ratio and calcination temperature (T_C). In Ni85Co15 (Figure 2b), a single RS phase forms at both T_C , due to the similar ionic radii of Ni²⁺ (55 pm) and Co²⁺ (58 pm), allowing uniform Co substitution in the NiO lattice. Increasing Co content to 50% (Figure 2c) leads to phase segregation. At 800°C (Ni50Co50_800), spinel-phase reflections [(220), (331), (511), (440)] at $\sim 31.38^\circ$, 37.60° , 59.55° , 65.37°] appear alongside RS peaks, indicating a biphasic NiO +

Co₃O₄/NiCo₂O₄ structure. At 400°C (Ni50Co50_400), metallic Ni/ α -Co peaks emerge, indicating incomplete oxidation and a three-phase mixture.

Similarly, NiFe oxides (Figure 2d) show mixed-phase behavior. In Ni85Fe15_800, spinel reflections confirm NiFe₂O₄ formation with NiO. At 400°C (Ni85Fe15_400), metallic Ni/Fe peaks indicate partial oxidation.

Figure 2. Results of XRD analysis on (a) mono- and (b–d) bimetallic oxides.

3.3 Electrochemical performance of the catalysts

Figure 3 compares the best polarization curves for cells using NiH100, Ni100, Ni85Co15_400, Ni85Fe15_400, and Ni85Fe15_800 oxides as anodes, paired with their corresponding reduced (metallic) forms as cathodes. Among them, Ni85Co15_400-based MEA exhibited the highest current density at 2.2 V, both at the beginning (BoT) and end of test (EoT), as shown in Figure 3a. At 50 °C, activation losses were comparable across all cells. Figure 3b shows the IR-corrected polarization curves. Accurate IR compensation was carried out by calculating the voltage drop due to ohmic resistance from the R_S-values inferred from EIS analysis (see below). After this correction, NiH100-based MEA displayed the lowest activation resistance among all tested cells.

The change in performance observed at the EoT appeared to be influenced by the synthesis method. All MEAs fabricated using materials synthesized via the sol-gel method exhibited improved performance: specifically, higher current densities at lower potentials. On the contrary, at the EoT, the MEA prepared with materials obtained via the co-precipitation method showed a worsening in performance.

EIS analysis was conducted for all MEAs. Figure 4 compares EIS spectra recorded at 50 °C at 1.5, 1.8, and 2.0 V. The results obtained allowed a deeper understanding of the above described changes.

Figure 3. AEMWE cell polarization curves at 50°C in 1M KOH. The shown curves refer to the beginning of test (BoT, dashed lines) and end of test (EoT, solid lines); both potential values (a) without and (b) with IR-correction are reported.

The enhanced performance can be attributed to MEA activation during operation, involving both catalyst and membrane components. Improved interfacial contact between membrane and electrode likely contributes as well. These hypotheses are supported by a noticeable decrease in both R_S and R_P values. At 1.8 V and 2.0 V, two distinct semicircles appeared in the Nyquist plots, with the smaller one at lower frequencies, indicating faster relaxation processes. Additionally, a shift in R_S towards lower values confirmed a better conductivity of the membrane after the operation.

Figure 4. Nyquist plots at different potentials: (a) 1.5 V, (b) 1.8 V and (c) 2.0 V. The shown data refer to the beginning of test (BoT, open symbols) and end of test (EoT, solid symbols). Data shown in inset in plot c refer to BoT.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the great potential of nanostructured bimetallic electrocatalysts for application in anion exchange membrane water electrolysis. The use of CoNi and NiFe-based materials prepared via the sol-gel method, a simple and scalable synthesis method, yielded promising results for both HER and OER, exhibiting enhanced performance and stability compared to the co-precipitated materials.

SEM analysis provided insight into morphology of the electrode materials. Structural analyses revealed the formation of single- or mixed-phase oxide systems depending on the metal ratio and calcination temperature.

Electrochemical testing in a zero-gap anion exchange membrane water electrolysis cell revealed that membrane electrode assemblies incorporating catalysts produced via sol-gel achieve higher current densities and lower activation resistances, especially after operation. The observed enhancement at the end of test suggests effective MEA activation, supported by EIS, which evidenced reductions in both ohmic and polarization resistances.

These findings highlight the importance of synthesis strategy and material composition in optimizing the performance of AEM electrolysis, paving the way for scalable, low-cost H₂ production technologies that are aligned with future clean energy goals.

Acknowledgements

The Authors gratefully acknowledge the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR) for the financial support to this study through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) - Mission 4 “Education and Research” - C2 component - Investment 1.1, funds for the National Research Program and Projects of Relevant National Interest (NRP), P2022BHKRA, funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU.

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Keywords: EFCF2025, H₂, LowTemp. Fuel Cells & Electrolysers, alkaline water electrolysis, high-entropy materials, AEM electrolyzer

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